

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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- **EXECUTIVE SUMMARY**

This deliverable is the first result of task 5.3 - Networking with other funded projects and initiatives (M1 – M36). This task aims at maximising the MARINEWIND impacts through the networking with other EU funded projects and initiatives (e.g., EERA JP Wind, EWEA, ETIP Wind/Ocean). In conjunction with Task 1.2, the Task leader will map all the relevant projects and initiatives (clustering) and will contact all the stakeholders in order to establish a collaboration on the MARINEWIND activities. The collaboration will exploit synergies in terms of joint dissemination activities (e.g., joint organisation of workshops and events) and knowledge exchange to increase the uptake and replication potential of MARINEWIND across Europe and beyond. The activity will be based on the successful story case of EuBioNet , the network of EU projects and initiatives on the bioeconomy founded by H2020 project BIOVOICES (coordinated by APRE). The newly funded projects under HORIZON EUROPE in the 2021 and 2022 calls will be also mapped and contacted.

1 INTRODUCTION

The establishment of synergies amongst projects and initiatives showing similarities in terms of cluster of topics and challenges addressed, orientation towards the achievement of resembling objectives and complementary activities implemented, is a key action in order to boost the outreach of the specific project results, as well as fully exploit their uptake and replication potential across Europe and beyond.

The fruitful collaboration with similar projects and initiatives can be shaped in different forms and through different channels, including joint dissemination activities such as the co-organisation of workshops and events or publications; the ongoing exchange of information and knowledge generated by the project; networking actions. Moreover, the pre-definition of strategies to enhance future synergies are becoming even more relevant in the framework of the EU-funded projects, especially with regards to the Programme for Research and Innovation, where the call for proposals are directly requesting the clustering with other funded projects, which are developing tools, frameworks or information that are relevant for the implementation of following activities in the same working field.

Starting from the initial phases of the project, all the MARINEWIND partners have been committed to setting up collaborations with relevant initiatives in the field of renewable energy, both at the local and European level, while ensuring that all the synergies established were sustainable over time and compliant with the MARINEWIND objectives and key activities.

The networking activities with other projects and initiatives presented in this report are referring to the actions implemented in the first half of the MARINEWIND project (from M1 to M18) and are the results of a two-fold exercise, jointly carried out by all the project partners.

In the framework of Task 1.2 *Stakeholders database*, all partners were required to map the relevant stakeholders in the marine field at both local (MARINEWIND Labs) and European level, following the approach of the MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders and through a desk research based on open databases, networks, list of EU-funded projects.

The stakeholders database will serve as a basis for the activities carried out in the framework of Task 1.3 *Labs co-creation activities*, dedicated to the active engagement of MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders through the organisation of in-person co-creation workshops in the MARINEWIND Labs, aimed at collecting data, opinions and point of views related to the barriers and enablers for FOWTs deployment through a direct dialogue with local actors potentially affected.

The database laid the ground also towards the effective implementation of Task 5.3 *Networking with other funded projects and initiatives*, aimed at maximising the MARINEWIND impact and outreach.

The initial version of MARINEWIND Networking with other projects and initiatives includes four chapters, as follows:

- **Section 1 - Introduction** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated, its relation to other project activities, as well as to its structure.
- **Section 2 – Mapping of projects and initiatives** describes the mapping of relevant projects and initiatives carried out during the first stages of the project, as a preparatory work for the networking activities, by outlining the objectives, presenting the methodology applied and the results of the desk research.

- **Section 3 – Synergies with other projects and initiatives** outlines the synergies established and the joint activities implemented or foreseen in connection with other relevant projects and initiatives in the first half of the project. The collaborative actions have been divided between synergies developed at local level, and as such mainly related to the MARINEWIND Labs, and international.
- **Section 4 - Conclusions** reports the reflections and indications arising from the first results of the networking activities, laying the groundwork for the next steps to be implemented in the second half of the project towards the complete maximisation of the MARINEWIND impacts.

2 MAPPING OF PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

This section aims to offer a comprehensive overview of the preliminary work carried out to ensure the smooth implementation of networking and cluster activities with relevant projects and initiatives in the field of renewable energy. Starting from the outline of the main underlying objectives, the following sub-chapters will briefly i) describe the methodology applied for the stakeholders identification; ii) present the projects and initiatives identified at the local level, divided according to each country hosting a MARINEWIND Lab; iii) provide the full list of projects and initiatives mapped at the international level and to liaise with, as part of the activities envisioned in the aforementioned Task 5.3.

2.1 Objectives

- Identify the relevant categories of stakeholders, whom engagement is crucial according to the objectives set up by MARINEWIND project.
- Map the relevant stakeholders to be involved in the MARINEWIND activities especially for the local level, but also the main projects and initiatives available at the European level.
- Pinpoint the main thematic links with the pre-identified projects and initiatives, as well as the potential areas to focus on the cooperation and the development of future synergies.
- Exploiting the collaboration opportunities to further promote the activities carried out in the framework of the MARINEWIND project, ensuring the maximisation of the impacts generated and a worldwide outreach.

2.2 Stakeholders' identification and methodology

Prior to the mapping of relevant initiatives and project to leverage on for the establishment of synergies and the maximisation of the results of the MARINEWIND project, APRE drafted a guideline to support the consortium in identifying relevant actors and stakeholders directly working or indirectly involved in the offshore wind technology field, a strategic sector enabling Europe to set itself as reference point in the sustainable development.

The final objective of the mapping of relevant stakeholders is to increase the exchange of best practices and enhance the creation of synergies among the main actors and initiatives both at local, national and European level, resulting in a stakeholders database created at M12 and a monitoring file to effectively follow the consortium activity in relation to the identification of all the relevant actors.

Following the Quintuple Helix approach, a fairly exhaustive list of relevant stakeholders divided by macro-categories to be mapped, has been identified according to the typology of actors, as shown in *Figure 1* below, and the geographical contexts of intervention.

Figure 1: Relevant stakeholders to be identified

The list of pivotal stakeholders has been divided according to the following categories:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** scientific community, research centres, universities.
- **Public authorities:** local authorities, national authorities, European authorities, local associations, national associations, European associations, maritime transport authorities, policy makers, municipalities.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organizations, citizens, foundations.
- **Green innovation:** public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, national natural parks.

Concerning the geographical context of intervention, three different levels have been identified as focus for the mapping:

- **Local level:** corresponding to the initiatives carried out in the MARINEWIND Labs located in Italy, Greece, Portugal, Spain and the United Kingdom. All partners will be involved, according to their country of origin.
- **European level:** with the contribution of all the partners, the mapping will focus on the countries where the wind off-shore is a solution already developed but even in all the European countries where there is a strong interest in its adoption (e.g., EU-funded projects; international initiatives; etc).
- **Extra European level:** referring to eventual initiatives and projects realised in countries with whom the MARINEWIND responsible partner has a close relation and cooperation with the main actors involved.

Lastly, the guideline for stakeholders mapping identifies the main channels to be exploited as source of information for the identification of relevant actors:

- Already established network between the project partners and the relevant stakeholders.
- Desk research of, e.g., local, national and European initiatives (e.g., the international wind energy conference; exhibition for Southern Europe and the Mediterranean).
- EU funded projects, whose mapping will be crucial to maximise the MARINEWIND impacts and to establish collaborations and synergies between the various partners. All the interaction throughout the duration of the project will be monitored through an ad hoc file.
- Publications.
- Thematic events of the EC or international organisations (e.g., European Maritime Day).

2.3 Mapping of stakeholders & local initiatives

This paragraph aims to provide a short analysis of the stakeholders database, built under T1.2 as a joint effort of all the Partners. The database has been created as a shared document for the MARINEWIND Partners to collect data regarding both stakeholders, at national, European and extra-EU level, and projects funded by the European Union. An additional Excel sheet has been dedicated to the description of the co-creation workshops organised in the Labs, in the framework of T1.3.

The above-mentioned database includes a total of 618 local stakeholders from the five MARINEWIND Labs. During the mapping phase, stakeholders have been divided into the five macro-categories identified in the Quintuple Helix approach. As shown in Figure 2, the majority of the stakeholders is representing Industry (35%), followed by Green Innovation (27%), Public Authorities (17%), Academia (11%) and Civil society (10%).

Figure 2: Categories of stakeholders in the database

Regarding the geographical distribution, a large number of stakeholders have been identified in the Italian (26%) and Greek (25%) Labs, followed by Spain (20%), the United Kingdom (17%) and Portugal (12%).

Figure 3: Geographical distribution of the stakeholders

The stakeholders’ list was a starting point to lay the ground for the further involvement of local actors in the MARINEWIND activities implemented in the framework of the Labs.

2.4 Mapping of international projects and initiatives

International projects identified:

Name of the project	Topic	Funding programme	Timeframe
AIRE - Advanced study of the atmospheric flow Integrating REal climate conditions to enhance wind farm and wind turbine power production and increase components durability	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-04 - Physics and aerodynamics of atmospheric flow of wind for power production	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2026
AQUAWIND - Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin	EMFAF-2021-PIA-FLAGSHIP-ATLANTIC	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)	01/09/2022 – 31/08/2025
BLADES2BUILD - RECYCLE, REPURPOSE AND REUSE END-OF-LIFE WIND BLADE COMPOSITES – A COUPLED PRE- AND CO-PROCESSING DEMONSTRATION PLANT	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02 - Demonstration of innovative materials, supply cycles, recycling technologies to increase the overall circularity of wind energy technology and to reduce the primary use of critical raw materials	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2025
BLOW - Black sea fLloating Offshore Wind	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-12 - Innovation on floating wind energy deployment optimized for deep waters and different sea	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2027

	basins (Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean)		
Blue-Paths - Addressing Sustainability Transition Pathways in the Blue Economy	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01-01 - MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2021	HE	01/03/2023 – 28/02/2025
COASTANCE - Regional action strategies for coastal zone adaptation to climate change	N/A	MED Programme – European Territorial Cooperation 2007-2013	01/01/2009 – 31/01/2012
COME RES - Community Energy for the uptake of RES in the electricity sector. Connecting long-term visions with short-term actions	LC-SC3-RES-28-2018-2019-2020 - Market Uptake support	H2020	01/09/2020 – 28/02/2023
COREWIND - COst REDuction and increase performance of floating WIND technology	LC-SC3-RES-11-2018 - Developing solutions to reduce the cost and increase performance of renewable technologies	H2020	01/09/2019 – 31/05/2023
ENTRANCES - ENergy TRANSitions from Coal and carbon: Effects on Societies	LC-SC3-CC-1-2018-2019-2020 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) aspects of the Clean-Energy Transition	H2020	01/05/2020 – 31/10/2023
EOLO-HUBS - Wind turbine blades End of Life through Open HUBs for circular materials in sustainable business models	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02 - Demonstration of innovative materials, supply cycles, recycling technologies to increase the overall circularity of wind energy technology and to reduce the primary use of critical raw materials	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2026
EU-SCORES - European Scalable Complementary Offshore Renewable Energy Sources	LC-GD-2-1-2020 - Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system	H2020	01/09/2021 – 31/08/2025
FLOATECH - Optimization of floating wind turbines using innovative control techniques and fully coupled open-source engineering tool	LC-SC3-RES-31-2020 - Offshore wind basic science and balance of plant	H2020	01/01/2021 – 31/12/2023
FLORES – Offshore Renewable Energies partnership in the Pact of Skills	ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-FORWARD	Erasmus+	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2024
FLOTANT - Innovative, low cost, low weight and safe floating wind technology optimized for deep water wind sites	LC-SC3-RES-11-2018 - Developing solutions to reduce the cost and increase performance of renewable technologies	H2020	01/04/2019 – 31/05/2022
FLOW - Atmospheric Flow, Loads and pOwer for Wind energy	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-04 - Physics and aerodynamics of atmospheric flow of wind for power production	HE	21/10/2022 – 31/12/2026
HIPERWIND - Highly advanced Probabilistic design and Enhanced	LC-SC3-RES-31-2020 - Offshore wind basic science and balance of plant	H2020	01/12/2020 – 31/05/2024

Reliability methods for high-value, cost-efficient offshore WIND			
ICONIC - Smart, Aware, Integrated Wind Farm Control Interacting with Digital Twins	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04 - Integrated wind farm control	HE	01/12/2023 – 30/11/2027
ILIAD - INTEGRATED Digital Framework FOR Comprehensive MARITIME DATA AND INFORMATION SERVICES	LC-GD-9-3-2020 - Transparent & Accessible Seas and Oceans: Towards a Digital Twin of the Ocean	H2020	01/02/2022 – 31/01/2025
INFINITE - INnovative offshore wind technologies In deep waters	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-12 - Innovation on floating wind energy deployment optimized for deep waters and different sea basins (Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean)	HE	01/11/2022 – 31/10/2026
JustWind4All - Just and effective governance for accelerating wind energy	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05 - Wind energy in the natural and social environment	HE	01/11/2022 – 31/10/2025
MARINET - Marine Renewable Infrastructure Network for Enhancing Technologies 2	INFRA-2010-1.1.23 - Research Infrastructures for offshore renewable energy devices: ocean-, current-, wave- and wind energy	FP7	01/04/2011 – 30/09/2015
MERIDIONAL - Multiscale modelling for wind farm design, performance assessment and loading	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-04 - Physics and aerodynamics of atmospheric flow of wind for power production	HE	01/10/2022 – 30/09/2026
MUSES - Multi Uses in European Seas	BG-03-2016 - Multi-use of the oceans' marine space, offshore and near-shore: compatibility, regulations, environmental and legal issues	H2020	01/11/2018 – 31/10/2018
PivotBuoy - An Advanced System for Cost-effective and Reliable Mooring, Connection, Installation & Operation of Floating Wind	LC-SC3-RES-11-2018 - Developing solutions to reduce the cost and increase performance of renewable technologies	H2020	01/04/2019 – 31/04/2023
ReaLCoE - Next Generation 12+MW Rated, Robust, Reliable and Large Offshore Wind Energy Converters for Clean, Low Cost and Competitive Electricity	LCE-14-2017 - Demonstration of large >10MW wind turbine	H2020	01/05/2018 – 31/01/2026
REFRESH - Smart dismantling, sorting and REcycling of glass Fibre REinforced composite from wind power Sector through Holistic approach	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02 - Demonstration of innovative materials, supply cycles, recycling technologies to increase the overall circularity of wind energy technology and to reduce the primary use of critical raw materials	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2026
ROMEO - Reliable OM decision tools and strategies for high LCoE reduction on Offshore wind	LCE-13-2016 - Solutions for reduced maintenance, increased reliability and extended life-time of off-shore wind turbines/farms	H2020	01/06/2017 – 31/05/2022
SETIPWind - Support and coordination of the European Technology and	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-15 - Support to the activities of the ETIPs and technology areas of the SET Plan	HE	01/09/2022 – 31/08/2025

Innovation Platform on Wind Energy and the SET-Plan Implementation Working Group on Offshore Wind			
SUDOCO - Sustainable resilient data-enabled offshore wind farm and control co-design	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04 - Integrated wind farm control	HE	01/10/2023 – 30/09/2027
TELWIND - INTEGRATED TELESCOPIC TOWER AND EVOLVED SPAR FLOATING SUBSTRUCTURE FOR LOW-COST DEEP OFFSHORE WIND AND NEXT GENERATION OF 10MW+ TURBINES	LCE-02-2015 - Developing the next generation technologies of renewable electricity and heating/cooling	H2020	01/12/2015 – 30/11/2018
TWAIN - Integrated, Value-based and Multi-objective wind farm control powered by Artificial Intelligence	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04 - Integrated wind farm control	HE	01/11/2023 – 31/10/2027
UNITED - Multi-Use offshore platforms demonstrators for boosting cost-effective and Eco-friendly production in sustainable marine activities	BG-05-2019 - Multi-use of the marine space, offshore and near-shore: pilot demonstrators	H2020	01/01/2020 – 31/12/2023
WENDY - Multicriteria analysis of the technical, environmental and social factors triggering the PIMBY principle for Wind technologies	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05 - Wind energy in the natural and social environment	HE	01/10/2022 – 30/09/2025
WHEEL - Wind Hybrid Evolution for Low-Carbon Solutions	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-12 - Innovation on floating wind energy deployment optimized for deep waters and different sea basins (Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean)	HE	09/12/2022 – 31/12/2027
WILLOW - Wholistic and Integrated digital tools for extended Lifetime and profitability of Offshore Wind farms	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04 - Integrated wind farm control	HE	01/10/2023 – 30/09/2026
WIMBY - Wind In My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05 - Wind energy in the natural and social environment	HE	01/01/2023 – 31/12/2025
WinWind - Winning social acceptance for wind energy in wind energy scarce regions	LCE-21-2017 - Market uptake of renewable energy technologies	H2020	01/10/2017 – 31/03/2020

XROTOR - X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction	LC-SC3-RES-1-2019-2020 - Developing the next generation of renewable energy technologies	H2020	01/01/2021 – 30/04/2024
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Table 1: List of EU-funded projects mapped

List of international initiatives previously identified:

Name of the initiative	Brief description	Link	Timeframe
European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)	EERA is the largest low-carbon energy research community in Europe and a key player in the European Union's Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan. It aims to expand the EU energy research capabilities and provide world-leading scientific expertise on three pillars: low-carbon technologies, materials, and systems' topics.	https://www.eera-set.eu/	Established in 2008
The European Wind Energy Association	EWEA promotes wind energy across Europe by coordinating international policy, communications, research and analysis. The association WindEurope produces different information tools and manages campaigns aimed at raising awareness about the benefits of wind and enhancing social acceptance, dispelling myths about wind energy and providing easy access to credible information.	https://windeurope.org/about-wind/	Established in 1982
ETIP Ocean	ETIP Ocean is a recognised advisory body to the European Commission as part of the Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan). It aims to maximise knowledge-exchange across the ocean energy stakeholders through our webinars and workshops, and put forward recommendations to inform policymakers and the industry in our high-quality publications.	https://www.etipocean.eu/	Established in 2019
European Maritime Day In My Country (EMD)	The EMD aims at raising awareness about the importance of the oceans and seas and to engage the public, particularly young people through the organisation of activities (e.g., workshops, excursions, school activities, etc)	https://maritime-day.ec.europa.eu/my-country_en	Established as public side of the European Maritime Day, the annual two-day event organised by the European Commission during which the Europe's maritime community is invited to network,

			discuss and outline action on maritime affairs.
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Table 2: List of international initiatives mapped

3 SYNERGIES WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

This chapter aims to provide an overview of the synergies with other projects and initiatives that have been effectively implemented in the first half of the MARINEWIND project. All the clustering activities have been divided according to their dimension, either local, thus corresponding to the specific country hosting a MARINEWIND Lab, or international. For each initiative or project, a brief description has been provided, as well as the assessment of the existing thematic links with the MARINEWIND project, explaining the reason why it should be considered relevant for the establishment of synergies, and the outlining of the joint actions undertaken or foreseen so far.

3.1 Local projects and initiatives

3.1.1 Greece

In respect of local initiatives, Q-PLAN established synergies with MINOAN Energy Community (MEC) in Crete, in order to co-organize the 3rd co-creation workshop at Heraklion, Crete. MEC is one of the biggest energy communities in Greece with more than 1000 members, house and business owners who are provided with accessible electricity produced by Renewable Energy Sources (RES). As Crete is one of the selected areas where, at least 4, Floating Offshore wind projects are expected to be developed in the medium and long term, the members of this community are of vital importance to enhance the stakeholder's engagement and acceptance of the foreseen floating offshore wind projects. In addition, the established synergy will be beneficial for the MARINEWIND project, since MEC members could be targeted stakeholders for social acceptance of the floating offshore wind projects and could facilitate the collection of feedback from a directly affected community.

Moreover, Q-PLAN was in close collaboration with Intec S.A., one of the co-organizers of the Offshore Renewable Energy Greece conference, where Q-PLAN organised the 1st co-creation workshop. The collaboration with Intec S.A. and the other organizers and supporters of the conference, gave us the opportunity to meet numerous industrial stakeholders, mainly from Greece and France, while collecting valuable feedback from the co-creation activities and disseminating the MARINEWIND project to significant players from the offshore wind sector.

3.1.2 Italy

At local level, the Italian Lab established strategic collaborations and synergies with different initiatives and national projects, leveraging on Partners own contacts, involvement in other projects or previous National Research Council (CNR) developed synergies with the Blue Italian Growth (BIG)¹ initiative, the Blue Economy national Cluster set up as a network of public and private entities operating nationwide in the field of industrial research, training, and technology transfer. The network aims at connecting

¹ <https://clusterbig.it/en/about-us/cluster-big/>

the world of academia with industry, bridging the gaps and strengthening the links between the two dimensions. The national cluster gathers more than 100 stakeholders in all the fields of the blue economy, including representatives from research and academia, small and medium enterprises, industries, sectoral organisations, and regions.

The activities implemented within the BIG Cluster comply with the development strategies defined both at European and Mediterranean basin level and address in a sustainable way the main societal challenges, according to the criterion of restoring and maintaining a Good Environmental Status. The strategic strands of actions identified are the following: i) Marine and Coastal Environment; ii) Blue Biotechnologies; iii) Renewable Energies from the Sea; iv) Marine Abiotic Resources; v) Marine Biotic Resources; vi) Marine Shipbuilding and Robotics. Moreover, the national Cluster encompasses three cross-cutting themes, namely skills and jobs, Research Infrastructures, and sustainability and economic uses of the sea.

Similarly to the MARINEWIND project, the BIG Cluster investigates the potential conflicts arising from the deployment of offshore renewable energies and other uses of the sea (e.g., fishing, tourism, etc.), as well as their co-existence and synergies, supported by technological advancements in the fields.

As joint activities, CNR attended the “Mare in Azione” (*Sea in Action*) event, organised in Rome on the 20th of November, 2023, in which a technical-scientific round table were set up to analyse the activities realised by the BIG Cluster between 2021 and 2023 and further planned to enable the transition towards the Sustainable Blue Economy, along with a discussion on the next strategies and pathways to be applied in the marine fields. The event provides the opportunity to introduce the activities carried out in the MARINEWIND project, aiming at collecting additional feedback especially regarding the impacts on fisheries and aquaculture. The interactions with BIG Cluster are supposed to be continued throughout the duration of the MARINEWIND project.

RSE carries out R&D activities in the energy sector under the “National Fund for Electric System Research” (RdS), which aims to improve competitiveness, security, and sustainability of the Italian electricity system. In the current 3-year Program Agreement (Q1 2022 - Q4 2024) with the Italian Ministry MASE (Ministry of Environment and Energy Security), the national project “Renewable energy and spatial integration” (*Energia da fonti rinnovabili e integrazione nel territorio*), several activities related to FOW have been developed, such as the geo-database of the Italian offshore wind projects and some techno-economic analyses of hybrid offshore energy systems.

Besides, CNR leveraged on the synergies with Sea renewable energies², another RdS project, involving key stakeholders from academia, namely the Department of Engineering from the University of Campania (UNICA), the Department of Engineering Civil, IT and Aeronautical Technologies of the Roma Tre University (UR3-DING) and the University of Rome Sapienza (UR1-DIMA), along with the support of the National Research Council (CNR).

The Sea renewable energies project, in which CNR participates as partner, is one of the pilots under the Flagship Project FP1 “5 demos in five continents”, funded in the framework of the Green Powered

²<https://explore.mission-innovation.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/MI-GPFM-%E2%80%93-National-Pilots-Report-2023.pdf>

Future Mission (GPFM), a ten-year public-private partnership – directed by RSE – gathering members from different countries at the international level. Each pilot aims to contribute to the overall objective of the GPFM, namely accelerating innovation in clean energy through the demonstration of innovative solutions able to transform the power system by 2030, driving towards up to 80% of variable renewable energies (VRE) integration.

The project, building on the outcomes of a previous national research project focused on the extension of the applicability of wind photovoltaics in the marine environment, aims to increase the Technological Readiness Level (TRL) towards the definition and implementation of the Floating Energy Archipelago (AEg) concept, defined as an initiative for fostering the eco-sustainable use of marine space for the production of renewable energy from the sea to be used directly at sea (e.g., hubs for refuelling the ships powered by hydrogen; aquaculture plants for fish farming). More in the details, the project accelerates the development of new innovative technologies for floating wind and photovoltaic systems, addressing the upcoming challenges through the already existing MaRELab, the laboratory for marine renewable energy where the first existing prototype in the Mediterranean Sea for floating wind power was installed. To reach its objectives, the project is divided into three different Work Packages (WPs): i) WP1 - defining a digital twin for marine energy; ii) WP2 - experiments at model scale; iii) WP3 - testing at the MaRELab marine laboratory. The foreseen activities include studying complex phenomena, testing scale models, and conducting trials to assess the effectiveness of new anchoring technologies and measure their environmental impact.

Similarly to MARINEWIND, the research initiatives aimed at providing a set of technical-scientific tools for reliable design to accelerate the transition towards new marine technologies and overcoming current technological barriers, ensuring low environmental impact, and a high contribution in terms of job creation resources and social acceptance. In order to enhance the mentioned collaboration, CNR and RSE will actively participate in project events and promote the exchange of information.

3.1.3 Portugal

Concerning the synergies to be established with local initiatives, WavEC is currently negotiating the possibility to organise the next MARINEWIND co-creation workshop as a side event of the Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition 2024³, which will take place from the 27th to the 29th of May 2024. The summit would ensure a wide outreach of the MARINEWIND project, both in terms of dissemination activities and engagement, as well as replication potential across Europe and beyond, since over 3,000 visitors are expected to join the three-day high level conference, including representatives from the ministries, policymakers, project developers, investors and innovators, willing to share insights on the transition envisioned for the energy system based on renewable energies, in line with the REPowerEU initiatives.

Secondly, WavEC is discussing potential synergies with the BlueBio Alliance (BBA), a Portuguese national network gathering all the sectors of the marine bioresources and biotechnology value chain, including raw material producers, R&D experts, biotech SMEs, manufacturers, public sector entities and final consumer product developers. The network, established as a strategical partnership, was officially launched in April 2015, with the support of the highest Portuguese governmental

³ <https://www.lisbonenergysummit.com/>

representatives. Amongst the main goals, the BBA aims at actively supporting the sustainable development of the blue bioeconomy by fostering and strengthening the relation amongst the different value chains, accelerating the SMEs' growth and their internationalisation and value creation.

3.1.4 Spain

Firstly, for the 3rd co-creation workshop, Sener and JustWind4All are working on a joint workshop to be held in *Arenys de Mar* on June 12th. The idea is to do the MARINEWIND co-creation workshop in the morning and to do the JustWind4All activities with the same audience. This synergy will allow to introduce new stakeholders, as JustWind4All is a research project that supports the acceleration of on- and offshore wind energy, including emerging wind technologies such as airborne and floating, through fair and effective governance. Secondly, the co-creation workshop will be done in the Fishermen National House. This is intended to be an initiative of open dialogue with fisheries among the rest of stakeholders.

Sener is involved in local R+D projects as FLOAT&M, focused on the challenges of operation and maintenance activities and digitalization of the process relevant to WP3.

3.1.5 United Kingdom

The Supergen Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE) Hub is a £9 Million project funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) with a renewed five-year plan until 2027 and currently led by the University of Plymouth and co-directed by the Universities of Aberdeen, Edinburgh, Exeter, Hull, Manchester, Oxford, Southampton, Strathclyde, and Warwick. The overall aim of the ORE Hub programme is to provide leadership for academic research and fostering the connections between academia, industry, and government enabling the acceleration of development of new innovations related to the offshore wind technologies, wave and tidal energy, considering all potential impacts on the ocean environment. Additionally, the programme ensures that the ORE research generated and supported through the funding scheme is adequately shared with government and policymakers, in order to be translated into informed policy and industry guidance.

Inès Tunga, from Energy System Catapult, has been directly involved in the SUPERGEN ORE Hub being a member of the Advisory Board, a steering group gathering experts from the entire ORE sector and engaged in elaborating strategic orientations and guidelines on the research requirements of the ORE industry and providing essential insights to industrial stakeholders and policymakers. This role allows the members to have a comprehensive overview on the ongoing research in the renewable energy field and shaping its future direction at the same time. Given this context, insights coming directly from MARINEWIND, and other projects linked to renewable energy are used as foundation to deliver on the research leadership, shaping conversations.

Additionally, the SUPERGEN ORE Hub identified eight different key Research Challenge themes, resulting from an extensive consultation involving industry and other stakeholders and aimed at harmonising the different industry roadmaps for offshore renewable energy beyond the sectoral basis. These key teams identified will be addressed through the flexible funding scheme of the SUPERGEN ORE programme with the ultimate goal of filling gaps and transfer research findings amongst the range

of ORE sectors. The relevance of the MARINEWIND project for the SUPERGEN ORE Hub can be explained by highlighting the nexus / matching between WPs and Research Challenge themes. More in detail, WP2 which is entirely focused on the analysis of the social acceptance and environmental impacts could be linked to i) Environmental and ecosystem aspects (Funding G) and ii) Marine socioeconomics and governance (Funding H). On the other hand, WP3 on the analysis of financial and techno-economic aspects could be relevant for i) Materials and manufacturing (Funding C) and ii) Survivability, reliability, and design (Funding E).

In this context, inputs collected have supported the first co-creation workshop, involving Professor Deborah Greaves, coordinator of the SUPERGEN ORE Hub, as keynote speaker. Further joint activities are foreseen, especially regarding the engagement in developing research challenges areas for the programme, leveraging on inputs and outcomes coming from the analysis carried out in the framework of MARINEWIND project.

A second ongoing initiative is the Wave Energy Scotland (WES), established in 2014 as a subsidiary of the Highlands and Islands Enterprise and following the request of the Scottish Government, with the aim to ensure the leading role of Scotland in the development of marine renewable energy, addressing the related technical challenges by driving the research for innovative solutions. The goal of the specific co-location project is to maximise the potential of offshore wind technologies by considering the co-location and the co-development opportunities of wave and wind energy. Moreover, a pathway towards the integration of wave and wind energy following the WES programme has been created, delivering two proof-of-concept technologies that can use co-development and co-location opportunities to maximise the energy harvested offshore. The main partners supporting the project are Wave Energy Scotland, AWS and Ocean Energy Scotland.

WES project has a thematic link with MARINEWIND WP1 - Policy framework assessment and co-creation, focusing on the mapping of markets, policy and regulations at regional levels, as well as recommendations of key market price signals to lead the power system towards decarbonisation, in addition to critical aspects of regulation to support the approach, through stakeholders' engagements and state-of-the-art assessment. In this context, the partnership established with WES has been crucial for understanding the Scottish waters characteristics, funding available, and key supply chain players and for gathering input during the first co-creation workshop. Additionally, this synergy with WES project falls within the framework of a previous collaboration linked to the exchange of information for the first co-creation workshop (Tim Hurst as a keynote speaker).

On the other hand, links can be highlighted within WP3, mainly with the analysis on co-location opportunities of integrating floating offshore wind in different systems and the potential economic benefits connected. In this context, ESC will continuously engage in the development of co-location models to assess systems benefits, keeping an eye on the ongoing work under MARINEWIND project.

ESC has been liaising also with the Decarbonisation of Ports project, developed with a focus on the area of the Port of Aberdeen, and funded in the framework of the Clean Maritime Demonstration Competition Round 2 (CMD2)⁴, an initiative promoted by the Department for Transport together with Innovate UK to invest up to £12 million in innovative feasibility studies and pre-deployment projects, as part of a set of interventions to be launched by the UK Shipping Office for Reducing Emissions (UK

⁴ <https://apply-for-innovation-funding.service.gov.uk/competition/1190/overview>

SHORE). Selected projects were required to undertake technical and economic feasibility studies, along with plans for innovative technology demonstrations of scalable clean maritime solutions. The aforementioned project analysed the future demand of energy from the Port of Aberdeen, assessing the low carbon energy sources for equipment (e.g., cranes, tugs, pilot boats) and quayside infrastructure, resulting in a roadmap for the decarbonisation of port operations. Amongst the foreseen activities, MARINEWIND project could leverage on the following aspects developed by WES: i) investments in the supply chain; ii) undertaken discussion regarding design and manufacturing; iii) stakeholders and community engagement.

Catapult Network, together with the Advanced Propulsion Centre, the Aerospace Technology Institute, the Net Zero Technology Centre and the National Physical Laboratory, is partner of the Hydrogen Innovation Initiative (HII) ⁵. HII is a programme, supported by Innovate UK, and whose mission is to drive the industry-led decarbonisation and fast-growing hydrogen economy through the acceleration of the development of key technologies and supply chains in the UK, while boosting the creation of high-value jobs. The initiative gathers 11 organisations and 40 locations across the UK and focuses on the following working areas: i) Accelerating renewable and low-carbon hydrogen production; ii) Storage of hydrogen energy; iii) Developing safe and efficient hydrogen distribution technologies; iv) Developing new hydrogen applications in power, transport, industry, and heating.

Amongst the ongoing collaborations foreseen throughout the duration of MARINEWIND project, the main synergies are envisaged with WP3, since the analysis of technological enablers for the deployment of floating offshore wind technologies are linkable to the co-location model development alongside HII project requirements to support scenario building and validation within key players.

ESC is also liaising with the Marine Energy Wales⁶, an initiative set up in 2016 and managed by Pembrokeshire Coastal Forum, with the support of the Welsh Government, the Port of Milford Haven and Morlais. The initiative aims at bridging the gap between industry, government and academia while supporting the innovation and development of the marine energy industry in Wales. By bringing together a wide range of actors in the marine renewable energy fields, it fosters collaborations to accelerate the deployment of relevant technologies, operating as a single point of access for the industry in Wales through our work areas in wave, tidal stream, tidal range and floating offshore wind.

In order to promote sector collaboration, knowledge sharing and networking, the Marine Energy Wales initiative supports flagship Welsh projects and technological innovation to connect the key players and decision-makers, enabling Wales to be the global trailblazer in the new and emerging offshore sector. The list of relevant members includes Blue Gem Wind, BlueFloat, Aquatera Ltd, Equinor, ORE Catapult, and META.

As previously mentioned for the Wave Energy Scotland (WES) project, the initiative shows a high relevance for MARINEWIND WP1 - Policy framework assessment and co-creation, since the Consortium could benefit from a comprehensive overview of the floating offshore wind sector in Wales, leveraging

⁵ <https://hydrogeninnovation.co.uk/>

⁶ <https://www.marineenergywales.co.uk/>

on the first-hand information and data on funding support, inward investments and insights on the policy framework to support the Net Zero Wales Plan, accessible through Marine Energy Wales.

Relevant links can be identified with MARINEWIND WP3 analysis of several financial barriers and enablers by the University of York, such as lack of funding, as pre-commercial projects require substantial upfront investments reaching hundreds of millions of pounds. Government support is also crucial, but the absence of subsidies and incentives can hinder investment and project progress. Moreover, inadequate communication between developers, marine planners, and coastal communities poses a barrier, leading to delays and loss of trust. High costs, including the levelized cost of energy (LCOE), manufacturing, and maintenance costs, present additional challenges. The lack of a well-developed supply chain, limited availability of suitable ports and installation infrastructure, and long installation and decommissioning times further complicate project development. Additionally, the scarcity of partnerships between wind turbine OEMs and project developers and opposition from stakeholders contribute to the challenges. Furthermore, the absence of standardisation in design, manufacturing, and installation processes, along with fluctuating energy prices and market dynamics, create additional barriers. High taxes, charges, or fees during the implementation phase pose financial burdens on projects. Furthermore, several enablers were identified such as grants and subsidies provided by the government to significantly reduce upfront costs, stimulating investment and project development. Low-interest loans offer developers access to affordable capital, while green bonds and climate funds provide alternative financing sources for sustainable projects. Infrastructure support and co-financing from governments or international financial institutions mitigate project risks and attract private investment. Contracts such as feed-in tariffs and power purchase agreements guarantee revenue certainty and attract investment. Innovation and research funding drive technological advancements and cost reduction efforts, while tax incentives lower the overall cost of investment and improve project economics. Furthermore, renewable energy certificates and guarantees of origins provide additional revenue streams and enhance project economics. Government support through grants, loans, and favourable electricity purchase contracts reduces risk and makes projects more attractive to investors. Shared knowledge and collaboration with the bottom-fixed wind and oil and gas sectors accelerate innovation and reduce costs. Additionally, issuing warranties can reduce insurance costs, while early stakeholder engagement prevents delays and builds support critical for project success. These enablers collectively contribute to the growth and success of floating offshore wind farms in the UK. Additionally technological barriers and enablers regarding the investigation of system requirements and flexibility, assessing the extent and conditions in which offshore wind and other renewables might be deployed, taking into account the requirements for storage and flexibility services, cost-optimal systems and innovation recommendations, along with likely future market opportunities, showing a link with the focus on investments and upgrades of grid and port infrastructure and the regional supply chain addressed by Marine Energy Wales. In this framework, ESC is actively contributing to drafting the regional energy strategy plans and collecting relevant input for the upcoming local co-creation workshop, in which Marine Energy Wales could be engaged in a panel discussion on Grid constraints and mitigation measures with National Grid, The Crown Estate, Regen, and Octopus Energy.

Additionally, the University of York secured the active engagement of the Regional Engagement Manager at Llywodraeth Cymru / Welsh Government for the joint organisation of an upcoming co-creation workshop, which will be held over 2 days in South Wales at the end of May.

The University of York (Dr. Paola Zerilli & Ahmed Djeddi) have been invited to participate in the Energi Coast Regional Supply Chain Showcase Event which was held in April 2024. The event aimed to facilitate engagement and collaboration within the offshore wind energy sector, particularly focusing on the North East of England by engaging representatives from diverse sectors involved in the offshore wind energy sector, including public authorities, supply chains, engineering firms, research institutes, and various industry stakeholders, including small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The primary objectives of the event were to improve supply chain industry engagement to explore innovative production and market strategies for accelerating the deployment of floating offshore wind in the North East of England waters. Identify key barriers and enablers to drive progress in crucial areas of offshore wind technology. Provide attendees with deep insights into market strategies tailored for floating offshore wind deployment, understanding the unique challenges and opportunities associated with this emerging sector. Foster an environment conducive to knowledge sharing, networking, and collaboration among industry experts, peers, and stakeholders, and contribute actively to advancements in the offshore wind sector by leveraging collective expertise and insights to identify actionable solutions and opportunities for innovation. The University of York played a significant role by actively engaging and collaborating with the Energi Coast Regional Supply Chain partners, forging connections between the objectives of the MARINEWIND project and those of the Energi Coast Regional Supply Chain NOF. More specifically, the University of York contributed by sharing findings from analyses on the financial barriers and enablers within the UK, as well as identifying limitations in the current model used for the Contracts for Difference (CfD) auction administrative strike price. Overall, the University of York's participation highlighted its dedication to advancing renewable energy solutions and supporting the growth of the offshore wind industry in the North East of England.

University of York has also been invited to present some of the main findings on the financial barriers for FOWT in the UK at the Marine Renewable Energy and Floating Offshore Wind Show Floor Theatre within the All-Energy/Decarbonise 2024 Conference which will be held in Glasgow on May 15-16.

3.1.6 WENDY project

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL established relevant synergies with the EU-funded WENDY⁷ project. WENDY - Multicriteria analysis of the technical, environmental and social factors triggering the PIMBY principle for Wind technologies, is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), fully funded in the framework of Horizon Europe Programme (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05 - Wind energy in the natural and social environment). Similarly to MARINEWIND, the aim on WENDY project is to investigate the key factors enabling and fostering social acceptance of wind farms through an in-depth analysis focused on three dimensions: social sciences and humanities, environmental sciences and technological engineering. To boost the understanding of wind farms decision-making processes and enhance the engagement of the citizens and local communities, the project will create a toolbox for promoting the wider adoption of the project solutions, which will be tested within 10 wind projects spread across 4 countries, and implement tailored outreach activities at the local level leading to the establishment of a WENDY Knowledge Hubs, gathering citizens, local authorities, business owners and value chain actors of wind energy sector, serving as a baseline for the WENDY Knowledge Exchange Platform to foster the knowledge exchange.

⁷ <https://wendy-project.eu/>

In this framework, the WENDY project set up a Network of Interest (NoI) working as a liaison structure for experts and stakeholders (e.g., regional and national regulators, industrial actors, energy communities) to share their knowledge and expertise with the WENDY project and hubs' communities in key deployment stages, through processes related to validation, networking and knowledge exchange. Q-PLAN, as part of the WENDY Consortium, set up a synergy with WENDY project to engage all MARINEWIND consortium members to the WENDY Network of Interest (NoI). The NoI serves as a platform for experts, stakeholders (regulators, industry actors, energy communities, etc.), and enthusiasts in wind energy to come together, share insights, and contribute their views.

As the main point of contact, the NoI foresees a topic dedicated to the MARINEWIND project focusing on the co-creation activities and results obtained so far. Additionally, the WENDY NoI was briefly presented during the second Greek co-creation workshop held in Thessaloniki on the 8th of March, in order to maximise its outreach and engage with all the participants, benefitting from the synergy between the two projects.

On another side, Q-PLAN laid the ground for an additional synergy with the Minoan Energy Community (MEC), Partner of the WENDY project, engaging in discussion for the joint organisation of third Greek co-creation workshop to be held in Crete, in Summer 2024. Choosing Crete as location for the last workshop is strategically important since it is one of the areas selected for the development of the first floating offshore wind parks in Greece. Additionally, the MEC represents one of the most active energy communities in Greece, bringing together more than 230 members, laying the ground for a great enhancement of the impact of MARINEWIND project. The first meeting to explore the possibility for the organisation of a joint workshop took place in March 2024, but additional way of collaboration will be discussed in the following months.

Besides Q-PLAN, the synergies established with the WENDY project have involved other MARINEWIND partners, precisely leveraging on the common objective to enhance societal acceptance and promote sustainable practices in renewable energy development, while addressing socio-environmental factors affecting the deployment of wind technologies. In this framework, MARINEWIND scheduled a first meeting with the WENDY partners to further discuss potential collaborations and share information on wind energy plants impact, considering environmental and socio-economic aspects. The meeting, held on the 12th of February 2024, involved NINA and Enel Green Power as responsible partners for the environmental and technical impact assessment, and APPA as responsible partner for fostering the interaction and exploitation of synergies with other related projects and initiatives. The exchange of information was crucial to lay the ground for a joint work in the upcoming months, as well as for collecting updated data to be integrated in the MARINEWIND D2.1 - Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers.

The future of the collaboration with the WENDY project could follow different strands of action, pointed out as shared areas of interested between the two projects:

- Multicriteria analysis to identify factors influencing social acceptance of wind energy.
- Engagement of local stakeholders and promotion of societal ownership.
- Harmonisation of social, environmental, and technoeconomic factors through multi-spatial planning and impact assessment tools.
- Drafting oof guidelines, reports, and handbooks to enhance understanding and empowerment.

- Establishment of a Knowledge Exchange Platform to facilitate stakeholder engagement and innovation.

3.1.7 FLOATFARM project

FLOATFARM- Developing the Next Generation of Environmentally Friendly Floating Wind Farms with Innovative Technologies and Sustainable Solutions⁸ project is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), coordinated by the Technische Universität Berlin with a wide Consortium composed by sixteen Partners from seven different countries. The three-year project, recently started in January 2024, was funded in the framework of the Horizon Europe Programme (HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-05 - Critical technologies for the offshore wind farm of the Future). FLOATFARM project aims to significantly advance the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind technology (FOWT) by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. To reach its objectives, FLOATFARM project will set up an open-sea laboratory demonstration, where a new 1:7 scale 15MW FOWT will be tested in combination with novel floaters, moorings and controls, ensuring the systematic assessment and validation of innovative solutions.

The main thematic links with the MARINEWIND project could be identified in the FLOATFARM objective to accelerate the EU energy transition, while analysing and mitigating the negative environmental impacts on marine life and enhancing the public acceptability of FOWTs.

The FLOATFARM project was presented by Dr. Claudio Lugni, representing the National Research Council, in a specific session of the second Italian co-creation workshop held on the 15th of March at the premises of the Civitavecchia harbour. A continuous interaction aimed at sharing information, documents, results and best practices will be ensured by the presence of CNR as Partner in both projects.

3.1.8 International Energy Agency (IEA)

The International Energy Agency (IEA), formed in 1974 as an autonomous body within the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), aims to ensure reliable, affordable and clean energy worldwide. The agency is currently composed of twenty-nine member countries, six associated countries and two candidate countries waiting for the accession to the IEA. Specifically, the IEA WIND Technology Collaboration Programme (TCP) focuses on the wind energy sector and is managed by an Executive Committee, bringing together sixty members from all the twenty-nine member countries, representing institutions from research, academia and industry working in the wind energy sector. The IEA WIND programme is further organised in different topics defined as Research Tasks. CNR-INM is actively engaged in the Task 47 TURBINIA, aimed at fostering cooperation in the field of detailed aerodynamic measurements and numerical simulations on MW scale wind turbines. It gathers research institutions and industrial partners working on wind energy, specifically in the field of wind turbine aerodynamics. RSE is involved in the Task 49 IDEA – Integrated Design of Floating Wind Arrays – whose goal is to accelerate the development of commercial-scale FOW projects by providing data, standardised methodologies and tools to resolve outstanding planning issues.

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136091>

The link with MARINEWIND project relies in the aim of the research initiative, namely the enhancement of the wind energy development at different levels, starting from the research phase to its industrial real application. Moreover, MARINEWIND has been included in the list of EU-funded projects mentioned in the IEA WIND TCP Annual Report. RSE and CNR, the two Italian members of the IEA Wind TCP, leveraged on this connection to further exploit the established synergies in terms of dissemination of project results and collecting information which are relevant for the MARINEWIND project objectives.

3.1.9 EERA JP Wind

RSE is an associated member of the European Energy Research Alliance Joint Programme Wind (EERA JP Wind), which is “a collaboration among major European public research organisations with substantial research and innovation efforts in wind energy”. In 2023 the NeWindEERA project was launched to define the research vision for wind energy to 2050 and its priorities. Within its activities, a list of significant projects for wind energy development was compiled and MARINEWIND was reported.

3.1.10 RISEnergy project

RISEnergy - Research Infrastructure Services for Renewable Energy⁹ is an international collaborative project started in March 2024 and funded by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 - Research infrastructure services to enable R&I addressing main challenges and EU priorities). According to its main objectives, the RISEnergy project will i) enable R&I to increase energy efficiency by reducing its cost through the wider employment of renewables; ii) provide efficient transnational access to 87 major European and international world-leading analytical facilities to support renewable energy technologies and systems; iii) connect with the wide range of stakeholders alongside the energy value chain; iv) provide innovative services (e.g., new cross-RI services; single entry point; tailor-made access roads for academia industry, and SMEs).

The RISEnergy project is strengthened by its wide consortium, made up of 69 beneficiaries from 22 different countries, including ERIC institutions, technology institutes, universities and industrial partners, to jointly improve the economic performance of technologies. Members of the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) are establishing the core European ecosystem.

CNR identified the main point of contact with the MARINEWIND project in the ambition of the RISEnergy project to foster the wind energy development at different levels throughout the energy value chain, engaging in an ongoing discussion all the relevant actors in the marine fields, as well as considering the deployment of innovative technologies from the research to its industrial application and the go-to-market phases. Moreover, the possibility of transnational access to world-class experimental facilities developed in the framework of the RISEnergy project could be extremely useful for supporting the technological development of renewable energy devices, including the floating offshore wind technologies. Since the RISEnergy project started only in March 2024, the synergies currently envisaged have not been yet realised, but will be focused on the joint dissemination of results and on the gathering of data which could contribute to the objectives set by MARINEWIND.

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131793>

3.1.11 JustWind4All project

JustWind4All, namely Just and effective governance for accelerating wind energy, is a 36-months Research and Innovation Action (RIA) funded in the framework of the Horizon Europe Programme (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05 - Wind energy in the natural and social environment) to address the complexity of socio-economic, environmental and technological challenges linked to the deployment of wind energy in order to support the acceleration of on- and offshore wind energy through just and effective governance. Through a trans- and interdisciplinary multi-method research design, the JustWind4All project aims to develop knowledge, practical guidelines, instruments, strategies, and trainings for ensuring a just decision-making process, taking into consideration the instances of whole range of stakeholders and wind energy governance actors, as well as the assessment of social, environmental, technical, and economic impacts. Additionally, the project promotes the knowledge co-production in Wind Labs, making the most out of innovative practices, technologies and regions, engaging with local, regional, national and EU wind energy governance actors through its Wind Forum, established as a platform to enhance networking activities, discussions and actions, and promoting a multiple stakeholders dialogue with an active engagement on citizens and focused on participation, energy justice and social innovation.

JustWind4All intersects with MARINEWIND project through its focus on assessing the socio-ecological and techno-economic aspects connected to the wind energy deployment. Additionally, JustWind4All delves into criticalities and opportunities related to the governance of wind energy, such as the effective engagement of citizens in the process, as well as the topic of energy justice, which are relevant also for MARINEWIND objectives when investigating the barriers and enablers for the development of offshore wind farms.

The joint actions to foster the establishment of synergies with JustWind4All as ongoing EU-funded projects are still under discussion. However, Sener is responsible for keeping regular updates and sharing information among consortium partners to ensure the execution of a smooth collaborative process. Amongst the upcoming planned actions, Sener is currently discussing the organisation of a joint co-creation workshop with the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spanish partner of the JustWind4All project, in the framework of the MARINEWIND project (task 1.3).

To date, three potential areas of interest for the development of synergies between JustWind4All and MARINEWIND projects have been identified:

- Facilitating the interaction with local, regional, national, and EU wind energy governance actors involved in either the Wind Forum and Wind Labs, established in the framework of JustWind4All project, through the fostering the exchange of best practices, information and outputs.
- Leveraging and learning from the socio-ecological and techno-economic modelling approaches and qualitative and quantitative research methods implemented by the JustWind4All project in order to provide a comprehensive and accurate data and impacts assessment related to wind energy deployment trade-offs and regional challenges.
- Learning from the multicriteria approach for the mapping and regional case studies to understand diverse perspectives on key wind energy issues, informing future strategies and policies.

3.1.12 Blue-Paths project

Blue-Paths - Addressing Sustainability Transition Pathways in the Blue Economy¹⁰, coordinated by the Landscape Analysis & Management group of the Department of Geography at the University of Girona, is a project funded in the framework of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01). The project aims at developing an integrated framework for Blue Growth (BG) linking human-environment interactions to address the sustainability challenges that stem from unclear interpretations, human pressures and lack of integrated methodologies in marine socio-ecological system analysis. Blue-Paths will investigate sustainable pathways for the use of ocean resources by identifying the related environmental and socio-economic effects on the use of oceans ecosystem goods and services and will deliver new knowledge on the management and planning of ocean resource. To reach its objectives and foster a more sustainable use of the marine socio-ecological systems (SES), the project will develop an innovative Sustainable Transition Framework (STF). The project investigates pathways of pervasive ocean technologies (OTs) transformations in key sectors of the Blue Economy, including Ocean Renewable Energy (ORE) Systems, coastal tourism, shipping, fishery & aquaculture, nature protection, and deep-sea mining. The framework developed, characterised by a high level of flexibility, will be tested in Spain, according to planning demarcations defined by current regulations. Leveraging on the collaboration with the National Research Council – Institute of Marine Sciences, Blue-Paths will to simulate the spatial-temporal environmental and socio-economic effects on the marine ecosystem induced by pervasive ocean technologies, providing provide innovative tools to monitor the sustainable use of the ocean space and foster adaptive management of marine resources, to be tested on the 2050 ecological transition plan of Spain.

The main thematic link between MARINEWIND and Blue-Paths project could be identified in the common focus on renewable energy systems in the framework of the Blue Economy, especially in offshore wind technologies. More in details, both projects show a strong commitment in contributing to the advancement of sustainable practices in maritime sectors, including offshore wind energy, and addressing its socio-ecological impacts.

As joint actions implemented in the first 18 months of the MARINEWIND project, Blue-Paths was actively involved in the first co-creation workshop organised in the Spanish Lab and the exchange of information between the two initiatives has been secured by Sener. Additionally, the following potential areas of collaboration, which are relevant for the further implementation of MARINEWIND, have been identified:

- The approach adopted for the development of the Sustainable Transition Framework for the effective analysis of the cost-benefits of high-potential ocean technologies, as well as the monitoring of ecological and socio-economic impacts resulting from the introduction of FOWTs.
- The relevance of the methodology developed by Blue-Paths for the MARINEWIND webGIS tool, such as the mixed-methods data collection approach, including multi-sectorial stakeholder analysis and collection of statistical and geospatial indicators.
- The application of state-of-the-art geospatial analysis techniques coupled with Machine Learning to understand the cumulative effects of new technologies on marine SES.

¹⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101062188/it>

- The aim of informing decision-makers, planners, and society on trade-offs of new technologies and developing transition theory-based strategic environmental assessment for ocean planning.
- The purpose of creating an interactive geospatial data dashboard for prompt communication of project results to stakeholder groups, facilitating exploration of potential distribution of offshore technologies across the Spanish sea and their socio-ecological effects.

3.1.13 Initiatives and events promoted by CINEA

On 21-22 November 2023, a MARINEWIND project delegation took part at the CINEA WIND ENERGY Cluster Workshop in Brussels. The workshop brought together CINEA's H2020 and Horizon Europe Project Coordinators and Policy makers in the field of Wind Energy. It was a great opportunity to meet and discuss together about the challenges and opportunities of wind energy sector in order to achieve climate neutrality. Furthermore, the workshop gave to MARINEWIND project the opportunity to start paving the way for a deeper understanding of wind projects activities across Europe and to start cooperating with many other projects and initiatives.

The two thematic discussions gave the opportunity to exchange ideas and views on many concrete topics of the wind energy sector:

Thematic Discussions 1

- 1. The contribution of the projects to EU Renewables Policies (digitalisation of energy action plan, Net Zero Industry Act)*
- 2. Sustainability and circularity*
- 3. Communication, dissemination and exploitation*

Thematic Discussions 2

- 1. Cost reduction*
- 2. Floaters*
- 3. Operation and maintenance*

The MARINEWIND project has been presented to the other project coordinators during the exchange and the networking sessions. The overall experience was extremely positive, and we are keen to replicate the clustering event in 2024 or 2025.

In the following tables the list of projects represented. Some of them and the related cooperation activities, have been already described in chapter 3 of this deliverable.

<p>AIRE 101083716</p>	<p>Advanced study of the atmospheric flow Integrating REal climate conditions to enhance wind farm and wind turbine power production and increase components durability</p> <p>Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-04</p>	<p>EU Contribution: €5,424,916.00</p>
<p>BLADES2BUILD 101096437</p>	<p>RECYCLE, REPURPOSE AND REUSE END-OF-LIFE WIND BLADE COMPOSITES – A COUPLED PRE- AND CO-PROCESSING DEMONSTRATION PLANT</p> <p>Horizon-cl5-2022-d3-01-02</p>	<p>EU Contribution: €12,362,239.68</p>
<p>BLOW 101084323</p>	<p>Black sea floating Offshore Wind</p> <p>Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-12</p>	<p>EU Contribution: €15,483,361.26</p>
<p>COREWIND 815083</p>	<p>COst REDuction and increase performance of floating WIND technology</p> <p>LC-SC3-RES-11-2018</p>	<p>EU Contribution: €5,031,858.75</p>
<p>EoLO-HUBs 101096425</p>	<p>Wind turbine blades End of Life through Open HUBs for circular materials in sustainable business models</p> <p>Horizon-cl5-2022-d3-01-02</p>	<p>EU Contribution: € 9,994,682.38</p>
<p>FLOATECH 101007142</p>	<p>Optimization of floating wind turbines using innovative control techniques and fully coupled open source engineering tool</p> <p>LC-SC3-RES-31-2020</p>	<p>EU Contribution: € 4,096,355.00</p>
<p>FLOW 101084205</p>	<p>Atmospheric Flow, Loads and pOwer for Wind energy</p> <p>Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-04</p>	<p>EU Contribution: € 5,995,208.75</p>
<p>HIPERWIND 101006689</p>	<p>Highly advanced Probabilistic design and Enhanced Reliability methods for high-value, cost-efficient offshore WIND</p>	<p>EU Contribution: € 3,999,638.75</p>

ICONIC 101122329	Smart, Aware, Integrated Wind Farm Control Interacting with Digital Twins (ICONIC) HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04	EU Contribution: € 3,897,447.50
INFINITE 101084321	INnovative offshore wind technologies In deep waTErs Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-12	EU Contribution: € 15,455,944.89
JustWind4all 101083936	Just and effective governance for accelerating wind energy HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05	EU Contribution: € 2,786,907.75
MARINEWIND 101075572	Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs) HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-03	EU Contribution: € 1,380,033.75
MERIDIONAL 101084216	Multiscale modelling for wind farm design, performance assessment and loading Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-04	EU Contribution: € 5,996,868.50
PivotBuoy 815159	PivotBuoy - An Advanced System for Cost-effective and Reliable Mooring, Connection, Installation & Operation of Floating Wind LC-SC3-RES-11-2018	EU Contribution: € 3,960,065.25
ReaLCoE 791875	Next Generation 12+MW Rated, Robust, Reliable and Large Offshore Wind Energy Converters for Clean, Low Cost and Competitive Electricity LCE-14-2017	EU Contribution: € 24,838,257.65
Refresh 101096858	Smart dismantling, sorting and REcycling of glass Fibre REinforced composite from wind power Sector through Holistic approach Horizon-cl5-2022-d3-01-02	EU Contribution: € 11,462,602.00
SETIPWind 101075499	Support and coordination of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Wind Energy (ETIPWind) and the SET-Plan Implementation Working Group on Offshore Wind (IWG OW).	EU Contribution: € 996,107.50

SUDOCO 101122256	Sustainable resilient data-enabled offshore wind farm and control co-design HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04	EU Contribution: € 5,769,120.00
TWAIN 101122194	Integrated, Value-based and Multi-objective wind farm control powered by Artificial Intelligence HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04	EU Contribution: € 5,998,642.50
WENDY 101084137	Multicriteria analysis of the technical, environmental and social factors triggering the PIMBY principle for Wind technologies HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05	EU Contribution: € 2,999,687.50
WHEEL 101084409	Wind Hybrid Evolution for Low-Carbon Solutions Horizon-cl5-2021-d3-03-12	EU Contribution: € 16,663,950.50
WILLOW 101122184	Wholistic and Integrated digital tools for extended Lifetime and profitability of Offshore Wind farms HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04	EU Contribution: € 5,816,861.25
WIMBY 101083460	Wind In My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05	EU Contribution: € 3,346,455.00
XROTOR 101007135	X-ROTOR: X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction LC-SC3-RES-1-2019-2020	EU Contribution: € 3,900,008.75

3.1.14 European Maritime Day initiative

The European Maritime Day (EMD) is an initiative launched by the European Commission in the format of an annual two-day event to promote the gathering of the European maritime community to be updated on the state-of-the-art, make the most from networking opportunities and pitch session, plan future joint actions in the field of sustainable blue economy and the marine environment. The EMD initiative brings together different stakeholders throughout the maritime value chain, including representatives from industries, governments, public institutions, NGOs and academia as well as EU citizens interested in the Sea.

As part of the EMD, the European Commission envisages the “European Maritime Day - In My Country”, a side initiative launched in 2018 with the purpose of raising awareness about the importance of the oceans and seas by promoting the organisation of events and activities at the sea, engaging especially the general public and young people. The organisation of EMD events is characterised by a high level of flexibility, since the activities can be realised by a wide range of actors, including educational institutions, public bodies, energy agencies, trade or industry organisations, businesses, NGOs, EU project partners, associations or networks, or citizens, addressing issues related to the marine field.

In 2023, a total of 494 events were organised in 31 countries, both in the EU and outside the EU, under the label of the EMD - In My Country initiative. The aforementioned number includes the first round of MARINEWIND co-creation workshops conducted in four out of five MARINEWIND Labs.

Below, a brief recap of the MARINEWIND workshops that have taken place as EMD – In My Country 2023 events.

- The Italian Lab First Co-Creation Workshop, titled “Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)”, took place in Bari, Italy, on the 13th of June 2023. This workshop, organised by APRE, RSE and CNR, with support from MARINEWIND Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Paola Zerilli of UoY, was hosted by the Port Authority of Bari and launched a quite relevant discussion among several stakeholders (mostly industry and technical experts, environment and socio-economic local authorities) on the Maritime Spatial Planning for the Puglia Region, and for Italy in general.
- “Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind”, as First Co-creation Workshop for the UK Lab, was organised by ESC, with support from APRE and UoY, as a side event of the “Floating Offshore Wind Conference 2023”, and took place on the 5th of October 2023, Aberdeen, UK. SENER joined the meeting as speaker, too.
- The MARINEWIND First Co-creation workshop in Greece, “Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs),” organised by Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL in collaboration with the Offshore Renewable Energy Greece event, was held on the 19th of October 2023. The event presented the Greek market framework, existing legislations and preliminary needs, all along with valuable information from active stakeholders in the domain of Offshore Wind Technologies.
- The MARINEWIND First Co-creation Workshop in Spain, titled “OFFSHORE WIND IN EMPORDÀ”, was organised by SENER and held on the 25th of October 2023, at the Casal de Pescadors in Roses, Catalonia. It gathered experts coming from diverse groups of stakeholders, such as government, public engagement, tourism, fishing, environment, academia, industry, and research. The highlight of the day was a dynamic roundtable discussion where the organisers and the participants tackled the challenges and the opportunities in the offshore wind sector of Empordà (Northeast of Catalonia), uncovering valuable insights for MARINEWIND journey ahead.

In March 2024, five co-creation workshops organised in four MARINEWIND Labs have been selected as official events of the 2024 edition of the “EMD – In My Country” initiative: those events will happen in Spring and early Summer 2024, and will be held in South Wales (UK Lab, in cooperation with the Welsh Government), the city of Marsala in the Sicily Region (Italian Lab, with the collaboration of local authorities and fishermen associations), the city of Arenys de Mar, close to Barcelona (Spanish Lab), and the island of Crete (Greek Lab) with the collaboration of Minoa Energy Community on May 29th.

3.1.15 European Green Week

APRE, as MARINEWIND Project Coordinator, included the MARINEWIND project in its institutional event called “ASK 4 Green: An Advocacy for Social Key-instances in Green Transition”, official partner event to the European Green Week 2023. During this event, organised by APRE together with H2020 projects W4RES¹¹ and GREENET¹² (the network of Horizon Europe Cluster 5 National Contact Points) and aimed at raising awareness about sustainability strategies and behavioural changes in society necessary for the Green Transition, the MARINEWIND project was presented by Inès Tunga from UK

¹¹ <https://w4res.eu/>

¹² <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/cluster-5>

consortium associated partner ESC. This workshop took place on June the 8th, 2023, in Brussels, and brought together policy makers, educators, and other key stakeholders. The event was held in hybrid mode, in order to gather an international audience.

3.1.16 International conferences

In the framework of the establishment of synergies with other European initiatives, potentially relevant for MARINEWIND project, WavEC identified events and international conferences in which the MARINEWIND project could be promoted.

WavEC attended the WindEurope's annual on- and offshore wind energy event, which was held in Bilbao from the 20th to the 22nd of March 2024. The three-day event included different conferences and 500+ exhibitions, gathering more than 12,000 attendees and experts involved in the wind energy sector, allowing for experience sharing and networking opportunities. WavEC managed to be present with a stand and disseminate the MARINEWIND project handing out leaflets.

Furthermore, also the UK associated partner ESC participated at the WindEurope Annual Event, which was held in Copenhagen, Denmark, from the 25th to 27th April 2023, with a poster presentation titled: "MARINEWIND: Accelerating Investments in Floating Offshore Wind to Tackle European Energy Crisis".

Additionally, WavEC joined WindEurope and its working group in 2023, being a partner of a group of European experts focused on the development of wind energy as a key component of the European energy mix, promoting the transition to a sustainable, reliable, and accessible electrical system for all. The organization focuses on research, promotion, and communication to achieve its goals, with WavEC contributing to technical meetings and discussions regarding grid integration and environmental impact mitigation.

The second international event, in which the presence of WavEC is foreseen, is the 2024 International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE 2024) which will be organised from the 17th to the 19th of September 2024 in Melbourne, Australia. The conference will gather ocean energy leaders, decision-makers and researchers from every corner of the globe for a rich and exciting programme of sessions, workshops, networking, technical site visits and an insight into Australia and its rapidly evolving ocean energy activities.

The third event, entitled Floating Offshore Wind 2024 (FOW24), Renewable UK, will take place on the 9th and 10th of October 2024, in Aberdeen.

FOW24 serves as the premier gathering for both present and future participants in the worldwide floating wind industry. It offers a chance to connect and engage with key stakeholders, fostering discussions on the pivotal technical obstacles and solutions in advancing the industrialization and commercialization of floating wind technology.

University of York has also been invited to present some of the main findings on the financial barriers for FOWT in the UK at the Marine Renewable Energy and Floating Offshore Wind Show Floor Theatre within the [All-Energy/Decarbonise 2024 Conference](#) which will be held in Glasgow on May 15-16.

3.1.17 EOLICA MEDITERRANEAN and ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN

The MARINEWIND project has been represented by the Italian partners APRE, RSE and CNR in a discussion panel of EOLICA MEDITERRANEAN 2023 and ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN 2023.

ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN 2023 was the international trade show dedicated to technologies to produce solar electricity, energy storage systems, grids and microgrids, electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, energy saving and other renewable sources that involves the main stakeholders at national and international level, both as exhibitors and participants to the conference program. Internationality is the key value of ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN 2023 in Rome as thousands of professionals from Southern Europe and Mediterranean countries attend the trade show, its conferences, workshops and seminars.

The ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN 2023 edition was an opportunity for all companies and professionals of the sector to network and take advantage of this reference event for Southern Europe and the entire Mediterranean region.

ZEROEMISSION MEDITERRANEAN is co-located with EOLICA MEDITERRANEAN 2023: with this synergy the two events represent the networking business opportunity for the zero-emission electricity industry 2.0.

EOLICA MEDITERRANEAN 2023, is the international trade show dedicated to onshore and offshore wind energy and its entire industrial supply chain. The themed shows offer all visitors a complete overview of fully sustainable innovations and related technologies: systems, materials, machines, technologies, products and services.

The 2023 edition product breakdown gave an interesting overview of the sector, with more interesting contents and conferences, meetings and seminars, with a particular focus on the potential growth of floating offshore wind plants in the Mediterranean Sea.

The consortium will evaluate the participation also in the 2024 edition in Rome.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Both the involvement of the five categories of stakeholders Industry, Academia, Public authorities, Civil society and Green innovation and the cooperation with other EU projects and initiatives are in the best interests of the MARINEWIND project.

Since the very first activities in our five countries we have strongly encouraged the cooperation of stakeholder at local and national level. The continuous exchange of knowledge and information has strongly increased the capacity of the consortium in collecting technical, environmental, socio economic and financial data, boosting at the same time the activity of awareness and social acceptance of FOWTs and wind farms.

Thanks to the MARINEWIND partners networks and to the precious support of CINEA, the project had the great opportunity to share information and results with other wind projects funded by the European Commission and with other initiatives at local and national level. Some of the MARINEWIND activities have already been co-organised with other projects, but this path is destined to be further

explored and exploited. MARINEWIND project consortium is in constant contact with many other consortiums and is paving the basis for future collaboration in FOWTs joining experiences and forces to further develop this sector.